

Dynamics and Hydrocarbon Degrading Potential of Microorganisms Associated with Long-Term Polluted Site in South-South Nigeria

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18171231>

Abstract

The dynamics and hydrocarbon degrading potential of microorganisms associated with long-term polluted soils near automobile workshops in Uyo metropolis was evaluated using standard microbiological techniques. The result revealed that total heterotrophic and hydrocarbon utilizing bacterial counts ranged from 5.60 ± 0.22 to 5.70 ± 0.11 and 4.53 ± 0.13 to 5.32 ± 0.3 Log₁₀ CFU/g whereas mean heterotrophic mould and yeast counts ranged from 3.69 ± 0.6 to 4.78 ± 0.42 Log₁₀ CFU/g respectively. Heterotrophic microbial abundance was higher than the hydrocarbon degraders and the difference was significant ($p = 0.05$). Hydrocarbon degrading bacteria identified includes members of genera *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, *Micrococcus*, *Proteus* and fungal species; *Yarrowia lipolytica*, *Mucor hiemalis* and *Candida tropicalis*. *Micrococcus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Candida tropicalis* and *Candida pseudotropicalis* exhibited high degradative potential with growth diameter of 15, 10, 10 and 9 mm respectively. The respiration rate in the control soil was $0.02 \text{ mg CO}_2 \text{ g d}^{-1}$ compared to $0.24 \text{ mg CO}_2 \text{ g d}^{-1}$ in the polluted soil. Total petroleum hydrocarbon of 1.3 mg/kg in the polluted soil was 6.5 times higher than 0.2 mg/kg in the control. Though the heavy metal concentration which ranged from 0.1 mg/kg to 3.26 mg/kg in the order $\text{Zn} > \text{V} > \text{Pb} > \text{Fe} > \text{Ni} > \text{Co}$ were within the WHO permissible limits, caution should be taken to avoid accumulation and biomagnification in the environment. Overall, hydrocarbon exposed microorganisms, *Pseudomonas* sp. and *Candida tropicalis* exhibited competitive advantage in their degrading potentials and are good candidates to be harnessed in remediation of contaminated site.

Keywords: Hydrocarbon, Hydrocarbonoclastic microorganisms, Heavy metals, Degradative potential.

INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution with petroleum and petroleum products has been identified as one of the most serious existing problems especially associated with intentional or accidental spills on a large scale (Nkanang *et al.*, 2021). The high number of malfunctioning automobiles with subsequent increase in the release of harmful substances into the environment poses a great environmental concern in Nigeria. The hazard of environmental pollution through disposing used automobile oil on the soil in many mechanic workshops in developing countries such as Nigeria is of great concern to public health and ecology (Olowu and Adebayo, 2023). Due to the mobility of petrogenic hydrocarbons together with their toxicity, mutagenicity, and carcinogenicity; soil contamination is considered a major challenge for healthy environments (Zhang *et al.*, 2022). The carcinogenic effects of petroleum hydrocarbons are well established and include increased skin, lung, bladder, liver and stomach cancers in petroleum-associated workers, in addition to reproductive, neurologic and developmental effects (Vermeulen, *et al.*, 2023).

Most petroleum hydrocarbons in environment are metabolized by indigenous microorganism for growth, reproduction, and as a requirement to relieve physiological stress (Varjani, 2017). Hydrocarbon degradation is attributed to different indigenous bacteria with diverse catalytic enzymes; thus, their roles in oil-contaminated sites also vary widely. Many genera of bacteria have been identified with the ability to degrade petroleum hydrocarbons such as *Achromobacter*, *Acinetobacter*, *Arthrobacter*, *Burkholderia*, *Dietzia*, *Enterobacter*, *Mycobacterium*, *Pandoraea*, *Pseudomonas*, *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *Bacillus* and *Rhodococcus* (Umana *et al.*, 2017a,b; Varjani, 2017; Xu *et al.*, 2017). In addition, some obligate hydrocarbonoclastic bacteria (OHCB), including *Alcanivorax*, *Marinobacter*, *Thalassolituus*, *Cycloclasticus*, *Oleispira* showed a low abundance or undetectable status before pollution, but were found to be dominant after petroleum oil contamination (Zhang *et al.*, 2022).

Also, a wide variety of yeasts and filamentous mould are capable of utilizing hydrocarbons. Yeasts capable of degrading hydrocarbons include genera of *Yarrowia lipolytica*, *Candida tropicalis*, *Candida albicans* and *Debaryomyces hansenii* (Hassanshahian *et al.*, 2012). Moulds are good candidates for remediation due to their ability of producing extracellular enzymes capable of breaking down hydrocarbons at the start of degradation and they are capable of catabolizing recalcitrant hydrocarbons (Ramdass *et al.*, 2021). The ability of mould to degrade hydrocarbons increased by creating a consortium from polluted soil for use in oil degradation (Briffa *et al.*, 2020),

Automobile Mechanic Workshops (AMWs) in Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMIC) contribute to the problem of soil contamination with petroleum hydrocarbons and toxic heavy metals as a result of indiscriminate disposal of spent engine oil (SEO). Such contaminated soil ecosystems serve as reservoirs of microorganisms with adaptive tolerance to metals, hydrocarbons and resistance to antibiotics (Akpoduado *et al.*, 2022). It has been estimated that about 0.08 to 0.46 % of the total oil produced is discharged into the environment, eventually causing pollution to waters and shores (Saravana and Amruta, 2013). The long-term contamination of a specific site with hydrocarbon presents a major environmental concern. Therefore, knowledge of the abundance and diversity of hydrocarbon degrading microorganisms associated with long-term polluted site is critical for effective and efficient bioremediation strategies and environmental management.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection

Soil samples were obtained from three different hydrocarbon polluted automobile repair workshop in Uyo mechanic village located at Obio Offot, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State (5.0199° N, 7.8867° E). Composite samples at 15 cm depth were collected from predetermined locations using soil auger into sample bags and labelled B, C and D respectively. The control soil sample (sample A) was obtained from garden soil from University of Uyo, Nwaniba road. The samples were transported to microbiology laboratory and analysed within 24 hours.

Isolation and enumeration of culturable aerobic bacterial and fungal isolates

The total culturable aerobic counts in the samples were performed using the pour plate technique (Antai *et al.*, 2014). For bacterial count, nutrient agar supplemented with antifungal agent, Nystatin (50 µg/mL) was used. Sabouraud Dextrose agar (SDA) and yeast agar fortified with Streptomycin (0.5 mg/L) to inhibit bacterial contaminants was used to enumerate mould and yeast respectively. All inoculated plates were incubated at 28 ± 2 °C, 24 hours for bacteria and 5 to 7 days for mould and yeast plates respectively. Microbial enumeration was aided by the use of Quebec colony counting (560 Suntex).

Isolation and enumeration of hydrocarbon utilizing microorganism

A modified method described by Nkanang *et al.* (2021) was employed. Four sets of 45 ml of mineral salt medium were prepared in conical flasks and sterilized by autoclaving at 121 °C for 15 min. On cooling, 5 g of each of the soil samples and 0.5 ml of crude oil were added to the mineral salt medium in the conical flask. The flasks were then incubated in a rotary shaker (SGM-300 Gallemkamp, England) operating at 120 rpm at room temperature for seven days. Total viable count was determined by plating the serially diluted sample on nutrient agar, Sabouraud Dextrose agar (SDA) and yeast agar supplemented with the respective antimicrobial agent, incubated at room temperature for 28 ± 2 °C for 24 hours for bacteria and 5-7 days for fungal isolates respectively. Visible colonies were counted and expressed as colony forming unit per gram (CFU/g) of the soil sample.

Purification and Maintenance of Pure Culture

Discrete colonies obtained were purified by repeatedly sub-culturing into a freshly prepared medium. The pure cultures were inoculated on agar slants and incubated appropriately and preserved in the refrigerator at 4°C for further analysis.

Determination of Hydrocarbon Degradative Potentials

The hydrocarbon utilizing potential of the isolates was determined using oil agar method. The degradative potential of the microbial consortium in the soil sample was determined using drop culture method and respiration rate.

Oil agar method

Method earlier reported by Nkanang *et al.*, 2021 and Umana *et al.* 2017b were employed. Mineral salt medium was prepared and sterilized by autoclaving. On cooling, 1% of sterilized crude oil was added and then the medium was aseptically poured into the sterile plates and allowed to solidify. The isolates were streaked on the medium and incubated at 28 ± 2 °C for 5-7 days. The rate of the crude oil utilization was graded as +++ (strong), ++ (moderate), + (weak), while (-) indicated no growth.

Drop culture method

The drop collapse method is a rapid approach to detect biosurfactants production and was determined as previously described by Bodour and Miller-Maier 1998 with a slight modification. Briefly, the enriched sample was subjected to centrifugation at 2000 rpm for 10 minutes and the supernatants were used. To a drop of sterile crude oil on a clean white tile, a drop of each of the supernatants were placed on the oil, allowed to stand for 40 minutes, and the oil displacement spread diameter was measured.

Respiratory rate

The CO₂ produced was determined by respiration of the microbial biomass in a moist soil using a simple laboratory respirometer as reported by Rowell, 1995. Briefly, 50 g of each sample were measured and transferred into separate conical flasks. A test tube containing 10 ml of 0.3 M NaOH was tied with a thread and suspended in each of the conical flask. The conical flask was corked and stored in a dark room for seven days, thereafter 10 ml NaOH was transferred into a beaker using a 10 ml pipette. Ten ml of 1M BaCl₂ solution was added to give a precipitation. Then, 3 drops of phenolphthalein were added to the solution to give a pink colour indicating an alkaline solution. This was titrated with 0.1M of HCl until the colour changes from pink to colourless. The end point of the acid was recorded and used to determine the amount of CO₂ evolved. Respiration rate of the sample was calculated using the relation below:

$$\text{Respiration rate} = \frac{\text{milligram of CO}_2}{\text{gram of soil} \times \text{Number of days.}}$$

Heavy Metal Analysis

One gram of the composite soil sample was transferred to Teflon beaker and digested with perchloric acid and nitric acid in the ratio (1: 1) HNO₃-HClO₄, followed by sulphuric acid, and the mixture was heated at 200 °C for 30 minutes. The digested sample was cooled to room temperature and made up to 50 ml scale with distilled water and analysed for Fe, V, Zn, Pb, Co, and Ni using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS model Agilent AA55) after selecting the various wavelengths at which the heavy metals were determined. The Instrument was calibrated with standard solutions prepared from commercially available chemicals (Merck, Germany). Results obtained were expressed as mg/kg of the net weight.

Statistical analysis: The data was subjected to the two-factor paired t-Test at 5% significant level to determine the effects on the soil microbial flora.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of the microbial abundance are presented in figure 1a and b. The result revealed that the total heterotrophic bacterial count (THBC) of samples ranged from 5.60 ± 0.22 to 5.70 ± 0.11 Log₁₀ CFU/g compared to the control with 6.0 ± 0.21 Log₁₀ CFU/g (Figure 1a). Hydrocarbon utilizing bacterial count ranged from 4.53 ± 0.13 to 5.32 ± 0.3 Log₁₀ CFU/g compared to the control with 4.70 ± 0.32 Log₁₀ CFU/g. (Figure 1a). T- test showed no significant differences ($p < 0.05$) with $p = 0.0062$ and degree of freedom = 3.

The heterotrophic mould count ranged from 3.69 ± 0.6 to 4.78 ± 0.42 Log₁₀ CFU/g in polluted soil (sample B, C, and D) compared to the control (Sample A) with 3.0 ± 0.32 Log₁₀ CFU/g (Figure 1b). The total heterotrophic yeast count ranged from 4.95 ± 0.35 to 5.66 ± 0.41 Log₁₀ CFU/g compared to the control with 5.09 ± 0.24 Log₁₀ CFU/g (Figure 1b). The hydrocarbon utilizing mould count ranged from 3.0 ± 0.35 to 3.30 ± 0.43 Log₁₀ CFU/g compared to the control with 2.95 ± 0.44 Log₁₀ CFU/g (Figure 1b). The hydrocarbon utilizing yeast count ranged from 4.0 ± 0.53 to 4.93 ± 0.25 Log₁₀ CFU/g compared to the control with 4.78 Log₁₀ CFU/g (Figure 1b). T- test showed significant differences ($p > 0.05$; $df = 3$) with $p = 0.057$ and 0.124 for mould and yeast microbial communities respectively.

Figure 1a. Total heterotrophic and hydrocarbon utilizing bacterial count of the samples

Key: THBC = total heterotrophic bacterial count; HUBC = hydrocarbon utilizing bacterial count

Figure 1b: Abundance of Mould and Yeast in the Soil Sample

KEY: THMC- Total heterotrophic mould count; THYC-Total heterotrophic mould count; HUM-Hydrocarbon Utilizing Mould; HUY- Hydrocarbon Utilizing Yeast

The bacteria isolates identified were members of the genera *Flavobacterium*, *Proteus*, *Bacillus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Micrococcus*, *Lactobacillus*, *Corynebacterium*, *Pseudomonas*, *Arthrobacter*, and *Leuconostoc*. Mould isolates identified were *Aspergillus clavatus*, *Aspergillus nidulans*, *Penicillium expansum*, *Sclerotium sp.*, *Torula sp.*, *Penicillium sp.*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus ochraceus*, *Aspergillus candidus.*, *Moniella sp.*, *Mucor hiemalis*; whereas the yeast isolates were *Candida pseudotropicalis*, *Geotrichium sp.*, *Yarrowia lipolytica*, *Candida tropicalis*, *Sacchromyces sp.*, *Candida maltose*, *Candida lipolytica* *Pichia pastoris* and *Candida oleophila*.

The distribution of the bacteria in the different samples is presented in Table 1 and the hydrocarbon degradative potential of bacterial and fungal isolates is presented in Table 2. The result indicates that *Micrococcus sp* and *Pseudomonas sp* demonstrated a high degradative potential (+++) with growth diameter of 15 mm and 10 mm respectively. *Bacillus sp* and *Staphylococcus sp* had moderate degradative potential, whereas *Proteus sp*, *Flavobacterium sp*, *Arthrobacter sp* and *Corynebacterium sp* demonstrated weak degradative potential. There was no observed growth for *Lactobacillus sp* and *Leuconostoc sp*. Similarly, the yeast isolates *Yarrowia lipolytica*, *Candida tropicalis* and *Candida pseudotropicalis* had strong degradative potential (+++) with growth diameter of 8.6 ,10.0 and 9.0 mm respectively while *Candida albicans* and *Candida maltose* as well as mould; *Mucor hiemalis* showed moderate degradative potential (++) with growth diameter of 7.0 ,5.4 and 6.9 mm respectively.

The result of the hydrocarbon degradative potential of the microorganisms by oil displacement spread of the consortium is presented in Figure 3. The result indicates a diameter 0.45 mm and 3.5 mm for sample A (control) and C respectively. However, sample A(control) evolved the least amount of 0.02 mg CO₂ g d⁻¹ while sample D evolved the highest amount of 0.24 mg CO₂ g d⁻¹. The heavy metal detected in the samples were Zn, V, Pb, Fe, Ni, and Co in the polluted sample relative to the control soil (Table 3).

Table 1. Distribution of bacteria isolates in the soil samples

S/n	Bacterial isolates	Sample A	Sample B	Sample C	Sample D	Occurrence (%)
1	<i>Lactobacillus</i> sp	+	+	+	+	100
2	<i>Micrococcus</i> sp	-	+	+	-	50
3	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp	+	+	+	+	100
4	<i>Flavobacterium</i>	-	-	-	+	25
5	<i>Bacillus</i> sp	+	+	+	+	100
6	<i>Proteus</i> sp	+	+	+	-	75
7	<i>Arthrobacter</i> sp	+	-	-	-	25
8	<i>Staphylococcus</i> sp.	+	+	-	+	75
9	<i>Corynebacterium</i> sp	-	-	+	-	25
10	<i>Leuconostoc</i> sp	+	-	-	-	25

Key; - = Absent; + = Present

There were marked differences in bacterial population from polluted and unpolluted soils possibly as a direct consequence of the effects of the petroleum hydrocarbon discharged into the soils by the automobile mechanics. There was a higher microbial count of hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria from the mechanic workshop soil compared to the control. This corroborates the report of Ndubuisi-Nnaji *et al.*, 2015 that hydrocarbon degraders are usually present in large numbers in many oils polluted soil and water compared to pristine environments.

Micrococcus sp and *Pseudomonas* sp demonstrating a high degradative potential, suggests the ability of these organisms to effectively use hydrocarbon as their carbon and energy source (Nkanang *et al.*, 2017, 2018; Umana *et al.*, 2017c and Omonigho *et al.*, 2017), adapt and tolerate the inhibitory effect of the oil component. They possess the ability to express enzymes that break down a wide range of hydrocarbons substrates as well as tolerate high concentrations of pollutants. These bacteria can grow and thrive on various organic contaminants, often displaying higher degradation rates than many other microbial species. Adeline *et al* (2009) reported higher *Pseudomonas* degradability towards aliphatic hydrocarbon sources, and the least activity towards the aromatic hydrocarbon naphthalene. with 69% degradation during the first three days. Chigor, *et al* (2020) reported that *P. aeruginosa* and *Micrococcus* sp. demonstrated high degradation potentials for Low Density Polyethylene (LDPE) in which, *Micrococcus* sp. recorded highest growth of 0.324 nm and 0.312 nm and *P. aeruginosa* recorded 0.40 nm and 0.258 nm at 37°C and 50°C respectively, after 15 days

This was consistent with another report that soils polluted with petrol usually have increased population of hydrocarbonoclastic mould and yeast (Agatha 2021). The high oil displacement spread of 3.5 mm (sample C) and the high respiration rate of 0.24 mg/CO₂/g (sample D) reveals a high hydrocarbon degradative potential of the microbial consortium in the samples. Samples C and D harboured species with high potential for biosurfactant production which increased the soluble content and bioavailability of the pollutants and improve degradation.

Table 2. Hydrocarbon degradative potential of bacterial and fungal isolates

Isolates	Growth Diameter (mm)	Hydrocarbon Degradative Potential
Bacteria		
<i>Lactobacillus</i> sp.	-	-
<i>Micrococcus</i> sp.	15	+++
<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp.	10	+++
<i>Flavobacterium</i> sp.	3	+
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	5	++

<i>Proteus sp.</i>	3	+
<i>Arthrobacter sp.</i>	2	+
<i>Staphylococcus sp.</i>	5	++
<i>Corynebacterium sp.</i>	2	+
<i>Leuconostoc sp.</i>	-	-
Fungi		
<i>Yarrowia lipolytica</i>	8.6	+++
<i>Candida tropicalis</i>	10	+++
<i>Candida albicans</i>	7	++
<i>Candida pseudotropicalis</i>	9	+++
<i>Candida maltose</i>	5.4	++
<i>Candida oleophila</i>	2.6	+
<i>Pichia pastoris</i>	2.5	+
<i>Mucor hiemalis</i>	6.9	++

Key; +++ = strong degrader (8 – 17 mm); ++ = moderate degrader (3.5 -7.4)
 + = weak degrader (1 -3 mm); -- = no growth

Figure 3. Hydrocarbon degradative potential of the consortium

Microbial consortium has been reported to produce crude enzymes, an efficient degradative factor accounting for the high degradation (Chen *et al.* 2023). Mixed microbial consortia are known to exhibit good performance in substrate tolerance and enhanced pollutant degradation (Zhang and Zhang (2022)). The adaptation of yeast isolates to hydrocarbon pollutants is linked to the yeast's natural ability to thrive in diverse environments. This agrees with Gargouri, *et al.*, 2019 who reported that *Candida tropicalis* and *Trichosporon asahii* could efficiently degrade total petroleum hydrocarbon removal.

The concentrations of heavy metal in the polluted soil were higher than the unpolluted sample. The polluted soil samples contained the following heavy metals descending order: Zn > V > Pb > Fe > Ni > Co which were within permissible limits (WHO, 2021).

Some species of fungi and bacteria have been identified to contribute essentially in the elimination of heavy metals (Alengebawy, *et al.*, 2021; Genchi, 2021). Bacteria have been observed to demonstrate exceptional ability in selective assimilation of heavy metal ions through the utilization of cell surface receptors. After the initial binding of these heavy metals to the receptors, the bacteria have been observed to effectively accumulate and reserve them

within their cellular structures, thereby enabling the bacterial cells to maintain their physiological functions under adverse environmental conditions (Gupta and Diwan 2016). Zhou, *et al*, 2023 reported that bacterial cells, such as *Pseudomonas*, *Klebsiella*, and *Microbacterium* species, have exhibited a remarkable ability to resist heavy metal ions that have been extracted from diverse contaminated sites.

Table 3. Heavy metal analysis of the composite samples

Heavy metal conc(mg/kg)	Control	Sample	WHO permissible limits
Fe	1.03	1.46	6
V	1.54	1.76	100
Zn	2.1	3.26	300
Pb	1.04	2.08	100
Co	0.08	0.1	10
Ni	0.22	0.32	35

Key: Fe = Iron, V= Vanadium, Zn= Zinc, Pb = Lead, Co = Cobalt, Ni = Nickel

Zinc (Zn) showed exceptionally high concentration in the polluted sample. Presence of high concentration of metal ions contributes to greater electrical conductivity in the contaminated soil (Pathan 2011). High level of electrical conductivity indicates a high concentration of dissolved salts ions in the soil samples, an effective measure for assessing the contamination.

In summary, there were empirical differences in bacterial and fungal populations between soils collected within operational mechanic workshops and unpolluted soil. These variations in microbial populations and the abundance of isolated genera are directly attributed to the continuous introduction of petroleum hydrocarbons into the workshop soils by automobile mechanics. The study area with unique mechanic workshops, characterized by open spaces where various petroleum products, such as used engine lubricating oil, diesel, and petrol (PMS), are indiscriminately released during repair and maintenance services, have a profound impact on the composition of the soil microbiota. Soils within mechanic workshops, which are exposed to petroleum hydrocarbon pollutants, exhibit a higher prevalence of microorganisms capable of using these hydrocarbons as source of carbon and energy. The ability of bacterial and fungal populations to breakdown complex organic and harmful matter into simple and/or harmless compounds and assimilate them as food has made microbial application useful in the science of environmental restoration. Also, the selective advantage for hydrocarbon-utilizing microorganisms within oil-polluted environments has significant implications for bioremediation efforts in ecosystems affected by crude oil spills.

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